

BENZYL*iso*THIURONIUM CHLORIDE AS A REAGENT FOR DITHIO-CARBAMIC ACIDS, XANTHIC ACIDS, ALKYL THIOSULPHURIC ACIDS AND SULPHINIC ACIDS

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The use of benzylisothiuronium chloride as a reagent has been extended for the identification of dithiocarbamic acids, xanthic acids, alkyl thiosulphuric acids and certain sulphinic acids. The melting points and analytical data pertaining to the derivatives are presented.

Donlevy (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1004) discovered in benzylisothiuronium chloride a reagent for the identification of carboxylic acids. This was followed by Chambers and Watt (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, 6, 376) and Campaigne and Suter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 3040) by its extension to the identification of sulphonic acids and by Bair and Suter (*ibid.*, 1942, 64, 1978) for the identification of alkyl hydrogen sulphates. It has now been found that the reagent can be used with ease and success for the identification of (i) dithiocarbamic acids, (ii) xanthic acids, (iii) alkyl thiosulphuric acids and (iv) sulphinic acids. The acids of the first three categories are known only in the form of their salts. Many sulphinic acids are unstable and deteriorate on storage. An easy and dependable method for the identification of these acids is therefore of interest. The results are presented in Tables I-IV.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylisothiuronium Salts of Dithiocarbamic Acids.—Alkali, ammonium or the amine salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by the usual methods, viz., by the action of the amine and carbon disulphide, or amine and carbon disulphide and alkali or ammonia in a suitable medium such as water, alcohol or ether. The precipitation of the Donlevy salt of dithiocarbamic acid was generally carried out in 50% cold rectified spirit with an excess of the reagent in the same solvent. In the case of aliphatic dithiocarbamic acids only aqueous medium was used. The aromatic or aromatic-aliphatic derivatives tend to decompose in purely aqueous media.

Since dithiocarbamates as a class are unstable compounds, care is necessary in their crystallisation. The solvent used for crystallisation is mentioned in Table I along with other relevant data.

TABLE I

No.	Benzylisothiuronium salts of dithiocarbamic acids†.	M.P.	Cryst. from.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Methyl	115°	40% Methanol-benzene	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₃	16.18	15.38
2.	isoPropyl**	110°	Ethyl acetate	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₃	13.82	13.95
3.	Dimethyl	143°	80% Alcohol	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₃ .H ₂ O	13.80	13.76
4.	Diethyl	148.5°	50% Alcohol	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ S ₃ .H ₂ O	31.30*	31.48*
	Methylphenyl				12 91	12.60
6.	Ethylphenyl	102° (d)	40% Methanol-benzene	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₃	29.00*	28.83*
		111° d.	Do	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ S ₃	11.84	12.03
7.	Phenyl	111° d	Do	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₃	11.55	11.57
8.	o-Tolyl	108° (d)	Do	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₃	12.47	12.55
9.	m-Tolyl	101° (d)	30% Methanol-benzene	Do	11.98	12.03
10.	p-Tolyl	102.5° (d)	40% Methanol-benzene	Do	12.27	12.03

* These figures refer to the percentage of sulphur in the compounds.

** isoPropylammonium isopropylidithiocarbamate, m.p. 145° (d) does not appear to have been described.

† References for preparation of dithiocarbamic acids: 1. Freund & Asbrand, *Annalen*, 1895, 288, 175. 2. Delepinne, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1903, vii, 29, 95. 3. Grodzki, *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 2756. 5. Delepine, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1902, iii, 27, 808. 6. Same as in 5. 7. Freund & Bachrach, *Annalen*, 1895, 286, 199. 8. Heller & Bauer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1902, ii, 85, 370. 9. Same as in 8. 10. Heller & Bauer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1902, ii, 85, 371. (The number refers to the corresponding serial number of the salts).

Benzylisothiuronium Salts of Xanthic Acids.—The xanthates were prepared by the usual action of carbon disulphide on potassium alcoholates (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1954, 2nd Ed. p. 483). The benzylisothiuronium derivatives of alkyl xanthates were readily prepared by treating the potassium salts with benzylisothiuronium chloride in very dilute alcohol. The xanthate was dissolved in the minimum amount of 5-10% rectified spirit and a concentrated solution of benzylisothiuronium chloride in the same solvent was added dropwise with stirring and cooling. The crude product was collected at suction, dried and crystallised. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Benzylisothiuronium salts of alkylxanthic acids.	M.P.	Cryst. from.	Mol. formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	K methyl	89.5-90	CHCl ₃	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S ₃ *	10.31	10.22
2.	K ethyl	98°	Do	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S ₃	9.80	9.73
3.	K n-propyl	95-96°	80% EtOH	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S ₃	9.21	9.27
4.	K n-butyl	103°	70% "	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S ₃	8.78	8.86
5.	K isobutyl	05.5°	50% "	Do	8.97	8.86
6.	K sec.-butyl	106°	60% "	Do	8.76	8.86
7.	K isoamyl	110°	70% "	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S ₃	8.39	8.49

Benzylisothiuronium salts of alkyl acid thiosulphates (Bunte salts) were prepared by treating concentrated aqueous solutions of the pure Bunte salts with an excess of concentrated aqueous solution of benzylisothiuronium chloride. The derivatives were readily crystallised from dilute alcohol or ethyl acetate.

p-Bromobenzyl thiosulphate was found to furnish two varieties of crystals with benzylisothiuronium chloride—one, the more soluble variety (mother-liquor on concentration gave fine crystals) and the other, the more sparingly soluble crystals. This is probably due to dimorphism. Results are presented in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Benzylisothiuronium salts from thiosulphates*.	M.P.	Cryst from.	Mol. formula	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Na benzyl	131°	50% EtOH	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂ S ₃	26.1	25.94
2.	Na <i>p</i> -nitrobenzyl	128.5°	40% ..	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₃ S ₃	23.44	23.14
3.	Na <i>p</i> -bromobenzyl	144°	Rectified spirit	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ S ₃ Br	21.85	21.38
		127°	Ethyl acetate	Do	21.90	21.38
4.	Na ethyl	101°	Do	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ S ₃ .C ₂ H ₅ OH	27.46	27.12

* References to preparation of Bunte salts: 1. Purgotti, *Gazzetta*, 1890, 20, 25. 2. Price and Twiss, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1403. 3. Same as in 2. 4. Otto and Rosing, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 989.

Benzylisothiuronium derivatives of aromatic sulphinic acids were prepared by mixing concentrated aqueous solutions of aromatic sulphinic acids with that of benzylisothiuronium chloride. The derivatives came out in well-defined crystals from 50% rectified spirit. The melting points are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV

No.	Benzylisothiuronium salts of sulphinic acids.	M.P.	M.P. reported by Kurzer & Powell.*	Mol. formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Benzene	150°	154-55°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	21.16	20.78
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolnene	168°	167-68°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	19.66	19.87
3.	<i>p</i> -Bromobenzene	163°	171-72°	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Br	17.10	16.53
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzene	170°	...	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	18.75	18.67
5.	β -Naphthalene	165°	168-69°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	18.43	17.87
6.	α -Naphthalene	180°	...	Do	18.26	17.87

* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3728.

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